

PLEP-0000 - Index of PlasmaPy Enhancement Proposals

PlasmaPy Community

PLEP	0
author(s)	PlasmaPy Community
date created	2017-09-28
date last revised	2018-09-26
type	informational

This PLEP is an index of all PlasmaPy Enhancement Proposals, known as PLEPs (to avoid confusion with Python Enhancement Proposals, or PEPs).

Informational PLEPs

number	title	author(s)	type	DOI
0	Index of PlasmaPy Enhancement Proposals	PlasmaPy Community	informational	
3	Members of Coordinating Committee	PlasmaPy Community	informational	

Accepted PLEPs

number	title	author(s)	type	DOI
1	Purpose and Guidelines for PlasmaPy Enhancement Proposals	Nicholas A. Murphy	process	
2	PlasmaPy Governance	Nicholas A. Murphy	process	

number	title	author(s)	type	DOI
4	Licensing of PlasmaPy Repositories	Nicholas A. Murphy	process	

Declined PLEPs

number	title	author(s)	type	DOI
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PLEPs in preparation or under consideration

number	title	author(s)	type
5	PlasmaPy Versioning and Releases	Nicholas A. Murphy and Stuart J. Mumford	process
6	A New General-Purpose Plasma Object	Andrew J. Leonard	standard

Tentatively Reserved PLEPs

number	title	author(s)	type
TBD	Data Structures		standard